

Spectrophotometric Study of the Reaction of Chromium(VI) with Fluphenazine Hydrochloride

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Fluphenazine hydrochloride forms a red coloured species with chromium(VI) instantaneously at room temperature in 2-5.5 M phosphoric acid medium. A 29-fold molar excess of the reagent is necessary for maximum development of colour intensity. The red coloured species exhibits maximum absorbance at 500 nm with molar absorptivity of 2.616×10^4 litre $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$. Beer's law is valid over the concentration range of 0.05-1.85 ppm of chromium(VI). The method offers the advantages of simplicity, rapidity and sensitivity without the need for heating or extraction.

THE colour reaction between chromium(VI) and fluphenazine hydrochloride (FPH) has not been previously studied. We have now studied this coloured reaction and developed FPH as a sensitive reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of chromium(VI).

Experimental

Apparatus: Absorbance measurements were recorded with a Beckman DB spectrophotometer with matched 1 cm silica cells.

Reagents: *Chromium (VI) solution:* A stock solution of chromium(VI) was prepared from AnalaR potassium dichromate crystals in double distilled water to give a standard solution of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$. The stock solution was further diluted as needed.

FPH solution: A 0.5% (w/v) aqueous solution of FPH was prepared and stored in an amber bottle in a refrigerator.

Diverse ions: Solutions of diverse ions of suitable concentrations were prepared using analytical grade reagents.

Procedure: An aliquot of the stock solution containing 0.05-1.85 ppm of chromium(VI), 10 ml of 10 M phosphoric acid and 1 ml of 0.5% FPH solution were diluted to 25 ml in a volumetric flask with double distilled water, mixed well and the absorbance measured at 500 nm against a corresponding reagent blank. The amount of chromium in the sample solution was deduced from a standard calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

FPH reacts with chromium(VI) to form a red coloured species in hydrochloric, sulphuric or phosphoric acid medium at room temperature. The study of the reaction in hydrochloric or sulphuric acid medium is not recommended because the reaction is less stable and many foreign ions interfere in the determination of chromium(VI). Hence, phosphoric acid medium has been selected.

The maximum colour intensity is observed in 2-5.5 M phosphoric acid. Below and above this acid range the absorbance is not maximum. A 29-fold molar excess of the reagent is necessary for full development of colour intensity. The red coloured species, which is thought to be a radical cation^{1,2}, exhibits absorption maximum at 498-502 nm at which the reagent does not absorb. The absorbance readings remain constant for 45 min and are insensitive to temperature in the range 5-45°. The order of addition of the reagents is not critical.

Beer's law is valid over the concentration range of 0.05-1.85 ppm of chromium(VI). The optimum concentration range evaluated by Ringbom's method^{3,4} is 0.18-1.55 ppm. The sensitivity of the reaction is 1.9 ng cm^{-2} and the molar absorptivity is 2.616×10^4 litre $\text{mole}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS
Amount of chromium taken = 1 ppm

Ion added	Tolerance limit (ppm)	Ion added	Tolerance limit (ppm)
Fe(III)	3000	Cd(II)	2500
Co(II)	150	V(V)	0.3
Ni(II)	500	Fluoride	1100
Cu(II)	1700	Chloride	2000
Mn(II)	1500	Bromide	1300
Mo(VI)	300	Iodide	0.2
W(VI)	150	Nitrate	2000
U(VI)	200	Sulphate	1800
Pb(II)	120	Nitrite	0.3
Ca(II)	1200	Acetate	1300
Al(III)	3000	Tartrate	500
Ba(III)	5000	Oxalate	1000
Zn(II)	2000	Citrate	2200
Sr(III)	5500	EDTA	8000
Zr(IV)	150		

Effect of diverse ions: In order to assess the possible analytical applications of the method, the effect of some ions which often accompany chromium was studied by adding different amounts

of the diverse ions to 1 ppm of chromium(VI) which gave less than 2% error in absorbance readings (Table 1). The major advantage of this method is that FPH can be used as a selective reagent for the determination of chromium in presence of a large amount of iron(III).

Determination of chromium in chromium steels:
Simulated samples containing chromium corresponding to chromal steel, AISI-A 4320 and AISI-

ES 2100 were prepared and the chromium content was determined. There is a good agreement between the amounts of chromium taken and found.

References

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